

IR26 (SC26), which damaged IR26 and Mudgo, was evaluated in seedling bulk and survival rate tests, with the original Gaozhou BPH colony as control. The varieties responded differently to the populations in the seedling bulk test (Fig. 1). TN1 showed susceptibility to the original Gaozhou BPH, IR26 was moderately resistant, and Mudgo, ASD7, IR36, and IR56 were resistant. TN1, IR26, and Mudgo were susceptible to the newly isolated SC26 population, IR36 was

moderately resistant, and ASD7 and IR56 were resistant. The survival of the SC26 population on varieties differed: survival on IR26 and TN1 was significantly higher than on Mudgo, IR36, ASD7, and IR56 (Fig. 2).

Although BPH biotype 1 was dominant in the Gaozhou colony, some BPH biotype 2 insects were found. IR26 could be damaged by BPH biotype 2; mature Mudgo plants could not. □

Wild rice: a new host for *Hysteronura setariae* (Thomas) [Hemiptera: Aphididae] in the Philippines

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The rusty plum aphid *H. setariae*, a vector of sugarcane and soybean mosaic virus, is a polyphagous pest that occurs year-round in coconut, coffee, and grasses [particularly *Echinochloa* spp., *Leptochloa chinensis* (L.) Nees, and

Eleusine indica (L.) Gaertn.] and occasionally in wheat and rice.

The wingless female is dark brown, shiny, and relatively small (1.70 mm long, 1.00 mm wide), with black antennal segments 1 and 2 and apices of segments 5 and 6, black siphunculi long and cylindrical, cauda white and parallel-sided. The frontal tubercles in the head are absent. The winged form is 1.50 mm long and 0.70 mm wide with a dark brown head and thorax. The forewing has a twice-forked median vein and the hindwing has a cubitus (Fig. 1).

For the last 5 yr, *H. setariae* has invaded wild rices *Oryza minuta* Presley and *O. officinalis* Wall in an IRRI greenhouse. Aphid density was high (>50 aphids or 2-6 colonies/panicle) during the Jan-Apr dry season, but no yield loss has been reported.

We studied the effect of aphid feeding at different densities on grain development. Each booting tiller was enclosed in a 2.5- × 11-in cylindrical mylar cage with

a nylon mesh vent on top and a sleeve on the side. Aphids were released into cages at six densities, and the sleeve was taped to prevent escape. *H. setariae* were allowed to feed on the panicle for 96 h and then were killed by a pyrethroid insecticide. Percent of damaged grain was determined using the formula

$$\% \text{ damage (adjusted)} = \frac{U(\%) - u(\%)}{100 - u(\%)} \times 100$$

where U is percent unfilled grains in each test and u the percent unfilled grains in the control.

Aphid feeding produced 4-43% empty grains, proportional to pest density (Fig. 2). The relatively low fertility of wild rices, particularly *O. officinalis*, was further reduced by aphid feeding. *O. minuta* and *O. officinalis* appear to have little or moderate resistance to aphids. □

Comparing parasitoid-host responses in laboratory experiments

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Parasitoid-host responses are determined in the laboratory by recording host parasitization at different parasitoid densities. Two components of the functional response are estimated: instantaneous attack rate *a* and a satiation factor, or handling time T_h .

One way to obtain these estimates is with nonlinear curve-fitting procedures found in statistical packages such as SAS, BMDP, and MINITAB. While these methods often provide standard errors of the parameter estimates from which comparisons can be made, they generally do not permit comparisons of the curve of total responses.

In a statistical test for significance between two or more functional response curves, two assumptions are inherent: 1) a null hypothesis that the curves represent samples from a common population, and 2) that the best possible sets of parameters describing the model's function can be estimated.

The parasitoid-host functional

1. Winged form of the female *H. setariae*.

2. Correlation of different aphid densities per panicle with damaged grain in wild rices *O. minuta* and *O. officinalis* (○—○).